

SMART: Tuning a symbolic music generation system with an audio domain aesthetic reward

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Abstract

Recent work has proposed training machine learning models to predict aesthetic ratings for music audio. Our work explores whether such models can be used to finetune a symbolic music generation system with reinforcement learning, and what effect this has on the system outputs. To test this, we use group relative policy optimization to finetune a piano MIDI model with Meta Audiobox Aesthetics ratings of audio-rendered outputs as the reward. We find that this optimization affects multiple low-level features of the generated outputs, and improves the average subjective ratings in a preliminary listening study with 14 participants. We also find that over-optimization dramatically reduces diversity of model outputs. Code and listening examples can be found here: <https://github.com/erl-j/SMART>.

1 Introduction

Systems that predict human aesthetic preferences of music are gaining traction (Tjandra et al., 2025; Cideron et al., 2024). Unlike other evaluation methods that compare generated outputs against a reference set (Kilgour et al., 2019), aesthetic preference models directly predict human preference ratings from a single audio input. This is achieved by collecting human ratings for various music stimuli and training a statistical model to predict average ratings for new examples. Such models have seen adoption as heuristics for dataset filtering (Tjandra et al., 2025), system evaluation (Lam et al., 2025) and as a reward for finetuning music generation models with reinforcement learning (RL) (Cideron et al., 2024). However, these share the limitation of predicting the average rating and disregarding the subjectivity of musical preferences, i.e. treating aesthetic judgment as universal rather than listener-dependent. While such aesthetic preference models have been developed for music audio, no such models have yet been developed for symbolic representations of music.

Symbolic representations, such as MIDI, abstract musical elements into symbols that have to be rendered into audio in order to be listened to. Applying an audio aesthetic preference model to the development of a symbolic music generation model can be achieved in a few ways. The most obvious way is to pre-render a symbolic music dataset with a symbolic-to-audio rendering pipeline to obtain aesthetic ratings for the symbolic music. These ratings can then be used as a heuristic for data filtering or as labels for distilling the audio preference model into a symbolic music preference model. However, if the symbolic dataset is large this requires significant upfront computation and making decisions upfront about the rendering pipeline which ultimately limits the flexibility of this approach.

We explore a different option; using RL to directly optimize a symbolic music generation model using an audio-domain aesthetic preference model as the reward. We call this intervention **SMART**:

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Symbolic Music Audio Reward Tuning. This brings us to our research question: *How does optimizing a symbolic music generation model with an audio-domain aesthetic reward affect its outputs?*

We limit our study to generating music for piano since such music lends itself to be efficiently represented by MIDI, can easily be rendered into high quality audio, and has been the focus of much work in music generation (Simon and Oore, 2017; Huang et al., 2019; Hadjeres and Crestel, 2021; Hawthorne et al., 2018; Colton et al., 2024). We use Meta Audiobox Aesthetics (MAA) (Tjandra et al., 2025) as our aesthetic reward, as it is the only openly available aesthetic preference model at the time of writing.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: First we present related work on RL applications to music generation in Section 2. Section 3 presents our method and its constituent parts. In Section 4 we present our experiments and results. Section 5 discusses our results and present some additional findings. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper and suggests avenues for future work.

2 Related Work

RL has been applied to optimize music generation systems using a variety of reward signals. *RL-Tuner* (Jaques et al., 2017), *Bach2Bach* (Kotecha, 2018) and *jaki* (Bruford et al., 2020), use Deep Q-Learning (DQN) methods for fine-tuning Long Short Time Memory models with symbolic reward functions. These methods operate entirely in symbolic space, without audio rendering in the reward loop. *RaveForce* (Lan et al., 2019) also uses DQN, and incorporates audio rendering into the RL pipeline by synthesizing MIDI outputs and computing perceptual or spectral rewards on the resulting waveforms, enabling optimization of timbral or rhythmic features beyond symbolic metrics. More recently, *MusicRL* (Cideron et al., 2024) learns a reward model trained on more than 300,000 human comparisons and fine-tunes a text-to-music model using Proximal Policy Optimization (Schulman et al., 2017) aligning generation quality with perceptual preferences. In the symbolic domain, *NotaGen* (Wang et al., 2025) features an RL fine-tuning phase based on Direct Policy Optimization (Rafailov et al., 2023), aimed at refining music generation with respect to structured prompts, including composer, period, and instrumentation. The reward signal is obtained by measuring distances from a symbolic reference dataset in the *CLaMP3* embedding space (Wu et al., 2025). In contrast to this earlier work, we apply a audio aesthetic preference model as a reward for tuning a symbolic music system.

3 Method

In this section we explain how we trained the base model and the components involved in SMART. Figure 1 diagrams how SMART is applied to a base music generation model.

Figure 1: **Overview of SMART** First, the policy and reference model are initialized from the pretrained base model. The reference model’s weights are frozen. Then, each iteration, a prompt is passed to the policy model which generates MIDI. The MIDI is then rendered into audios which are assigned rewards by the aesthetic preference model. These rewards are then used to compute the group relative advantages which are then used to update the policy model. This optimization is regularized by an additional KL loss term which prevents the policy model from straying too far away from the reference model. This figure is adapted from Shao et al. (2024).

3.1 Base model training

We start by training a base model on a large dataset of MIDI files containing piano music. We use a causal Transformer model based on the Microsoft Phi-3 architecture (Abdin et al., 2024) as implemented in the Huggingface Transformers library.¹ Our model has 4 layers and a hidden size of 512, with 8 attention heads. The model is trained on piano data from the *MetaMIDI* dataset (Ens and Pasquier, 2021). Specifically, we filtered out any MIDI file that does not contain a program number belonging to the piano group in the *General MIDI* specification (programs 1-8). Of these, only the piano tracks are kept and merged into a single track, removing duplicated notes. The MIDI files are tokenized using the *REMI+* tokenizer (von Rütte et al., 2023) as implemented in the *MidiTok* library (Fradet et al., 2021). After tokenization, additional filtering removes tracks with more than 300 notes per bar and more than 20% of empty bars, resulting in a total of 216,850 files. 10% of the dataset is left as a holdout test set, while the remainder is used for training and validation with a 90 : 10 ratio. During training we take random crops with a length of up to 512 tokens, padding with special "PAD" tokens when necessary.

3.2 Group Relative Preference Optimization

We use *Group Relative Preference Optimization (GRPO)* (Shao et al., 2024) as our RL algorithm, using the implementation from the TRL library.² Equation 1 shows the GRPO objective.

$$\mathcal{L}_{GRPO}(\theta) = -\frac{1}{G} \sum_{i=1}^G \sum_{t=1}^{|o_i|} \left[\frac{\pi_{\theta}(o_{i,t} | q, o_{i,<t})}{\pi_{\theta_{old}}(o_{i,t} | q, o_{i,<t})} \hat{A}_{i,t} - \beta D_{KL} [\pi_{\theta} || \pi_{ref}] \right] \quad (1)$$

G is the number of groups, with each group containing multiple *completions* o_i of a specific *prompt*. π and π_{old} refer to the current and previous policy (model). The advantage $\hat{A}_{i,t} = \frac{r_i + \text{mean}(r)}{\text{std}(r)}$ represents the group-normalized reward for each completion. This reward maximization term is regularized by the Kullback–Leibler (KL) divergence between a prediction, scaled by a parameter β . This second term is used to mitigate over-optimization toward the reward by penalizing completions which are unlikely according to the reference model π_{ref} .

3.3 Audio Aesthetic Preference Model

Meta Audiobox Aesthetics (MAA) is a model created for the predicting human ratings of audio, speech and music (Tjandra et al., 2025). It is trained on 10-second fragments of audio, which human raters scored on a 10-point scale across four different aesthetic attributes that are described as follows:

Production Quality “Focuses on the technical aspects of quality instead of subjective quality. Aspects including clarity & fidelity, dynamics, frequencies and spatialization of the audio”;

Production Complexity “Focuses on the complexity of an audio scene, measured by number of audio components”;

Content Enjoyment “Focuses on the subject quality of an audio piece. It’s a more open-ended axis, some aspects might includes emotional impact, artistic skill, artistic expression, as well as subjective experience, etc”;

Content Usefulness “Also a subjective axis, evaluating the likelihood of leveraging the audio as source material for content creation”. Here, *content* is specifically referring to audio-visual content for platforms like YouTube and Instagram.

MAA has some limitations. First, the 10-second receptive field means it can not take into account patterns that are longer than 10 seconds, such as the repetition and development of musical ideas in a coherent structure. Secondly, music collection used, and the cultural background and musical training of the raters, are not disclosed by Tjandra et al. (2025).

To provide more context on what MAA ratings may mean, we have it rate audio excerpts of a diverse set of live piano performances, as well as white noise and silence. Table 1 shows the results (Table 4 in the Appendix provides the URLs for the recordings). Given that we are tuning a symbolic music

¹https://huggingface.co/docs/transformers/en/model_doc/phi3, last accessed Apr. 21 2025.

²https://huggingface.co/docs/trl/main/en/grpo_trainer, last accessed Apr. 21 2025

generation model and that our rendering pipeline is fixed, we exclude Production Quality as the reward. Given that we have one sole source (piano), we exclude Production Complexity as the reward. Given that we are not necessarily targeting compositions for audio-visual content creation, we exclude Content Usefulness. This leaves Content Enjoyment as the most relevant reward to optimize for.

Table 1: Meta Audiobox Aesthetics ratings for recordings of 10-second excerpts of various piano performances. We also include the ratings given to silence and white noise. CE: Content Enjoyment. CU: Content Usefulness. PC: Production Complexity. PQ: Production Quality

Audio	CE	CU	PC	PQ	Mean
Oscar Peterson - Someone to Watch Over Me (Live)	7.48	7.76	3.94	7.70	6.72
Ludovico Einaudi - Nuvole Bianche	7.41	7.91	3.47	8.01	6.70
Chopin - Waltz Op.69 No.2 (Ashkenazy)	7.60	7.92	3.50	7.50	6.63
Conlon Nancarrow - Study for Player Piano No. 21	6.40	7.71	3.95	7.88	6.49
Philip Glass - Etude No.6 (Yuja Wang)	6.88	7.61	3.99	7.43	6.48
Keith Jarrett - Solar	7.12	7.35	3.90	7.48	6.46
Brad Mehldau - My Favorite Things (Live)	7.24	7.63	3.36	7.28	6.38
Lili Boulanger - Prelude in B Major	6.80	7.64	3.38	7.49	6.33
Hiromi Uehara - Blackbird (Live)	6.27	7.06	3.63	7.24	6.05
John Cage - Sonata for Prepared Piano No.1	5.96	7.8	2.62	7.75	6.03
Mozart - Piano Sonata No.16 K.545 (Ingrid Haebler)	6.95	7.33	3.03	6.71	6.01
Silence	3.24	6.45	1.7	6.74	4.53
White Noise	2.37	4.65	1.99	4.79	3.45

3.4 MIDI to Audio Rendering

We render MIDI into audio using a soundfont renderer. Soundfont is a format for sample-based synthesis commonly used for rendering MIDI files. Table 2 shows the average for the four different ratings produced by MAA computed over a batch of 10 samples from the pretraining dataset rendered with five different publicly available soundfonts (The URLs of these soundfonts are provided in Table 3 in the Appendix). For the experiments described in this paper we use the Yamaha C5 Salamander-JNv5.1 soundfont. We see that the choice of soundfont impacts Content Enjoyment the most, followed by Production Quality, while Content Usefulness and Production Complexity are less affected.

Table 2: Audiobox Aesthetics rating for five publicly available soundfonts.

Soundfont	musescore	fluidr3	grandeur	sgm	yamaha
Content Enjoyment	5.423	5.347	6.385	6.602	6.530
Content Usefulness	7.487	7.408	7.693	7.716	7.705
Production Complexity	2.352	2.355	2.376	2.477	2.453
Production Quality	7.323	7.817	7.884	7.695	7.883
Average	5.646	5.732	6.085	6.123	6.143

3.5 Training details

Each iteration, we procedurally generate 8 prompts formatted according to the REMI+ syntax (von Rütte et al., 2023), including a token indicating the start of a new bar, a random time signature token and a random tempo token. For each prompt, we generate 8 completions, totaling 64 completions per batch. All completions were sampled with temperature 1.0. We cropped all audio to 10 seconds, the receptive field of MAA. We set the KL divergence regularization parameter $\beta = 0.04$ and employed a linear learning rate schedule starting at 1×10^{-4} and decaying to 0 over 200 iterations. Training was conducted on a single NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 GPU and completed in 50 minutes. Figure 2 shows the reward improving over the training iterations.

Figure 2: Predicted Content Enjoyment rating from MAA across SMART iterations.

4 Results

We now compare base model outputs and SMART model outputs according to MAA ratings, low level features, and subjective ratings from a small listening test.. We also invite the reader to listen to the audio examples presented at <https://erl-j.github.io/SMART-demo/>.

4.1 Comparison of Meta Audiobox Aesthetics ratings

We generate 1000 examples from the base model and its SMART adaptation using procedural prompts, render them as audio, and then have MAA rate each. Figure 3 shows that SMART is able to optimize the Content Enjoyment reward. We also notice increases in the MAA ratings we did not optimize for. This could be related to the correlation between the four attribute scores in the human ratings reported by Tjandra et al. (2025).

Figure 3: **Optimizing for predicted Content Enjoyment also increases the other ratings.** MAA ratings of 1000 generations with random procedural prompts for the piano model pre and post audio reward optimization.

4.2 MIDI-level features

We investigate the effect of our intervention by comparing MIDI-level features of the outputs from both the base model and SMART model. Using 1000 procedurally generated prompts, we generate one completion from the base model and one from the SMART model, producing 2000 MIDI files. Using MusPy (Dong et al., 2020), we compute 8 features whose histograms are shown in Figure 4.

Number of notes refers to the count of note events in the midi file. We see that the base model’s outputs sometimes contain few notes. This is not the case for the post-intervention model whose note counts are concentrated around 70.

Polyphony rate is the proportion of time steps where multiple pitches are active. We see that the post-intervention model uses more polyphony.

Empty-beat rate is the ratio of beats that contain no note events. While the base model’s outputs contains some empty beats, these are more rare in the post-intervention model.

Pitch distribution: This shows the count of each individual MIDI pitch. Compared to the base model, the SMART model has more pitches in the lower octaves.

Figure 4: **Optimizing towards the aesthetic reward affects distribution of low-level features in model outputs.** Histograms of various track and note features from 1000 generations with random procedural prompts for the piano model before and after SMART.

Pitch range refers to the distance in semitones between the lowest and highest pitch in a track. The SMART model tends to use a larger pitch range.

Scale consistency: This is the highest ratio of notes that belong to a certain scale, tested against all major and minor scales. The distribution appears to have a heavier tail after SMART, suggesting increased use of chromaticism.

Velocity distribution: This refers to the count of individual velocity levels (the tokenizer uses 20 bins). Compared to the base model, the SMART model outputs tend to have lower velocities.

Velocity range: This is the distance between the lowest and highest velocity value in a track. The base model shows a zero-inflated distribution, suggesting no dynamic range is present in some of its outputs. This is rarer in the SMART model whose outputs include a larger range of velocity values.

4.3 Listening Study

Figure 5: **On the left:** Overall distribution of the ratings. Red indicates the base model, blue indicates the post-intervention model. **On the right:** Distribution of the ratings from each subject.

We conduct a small listening study, collecting ratings from 14 subjects recruited via convenience sampling from researchers in the computer science department at KTH. Before the test starts, each participant is prompted with the following message: *"You will listen to several audio samples and rate their enjoyability"*. In each trial, a participant listens to a ~ 10 s music excerpt, and is then asked, *"How much do you enjoy this audio? Rate from 1 to 10."* Each subject rated 30 excerpts in total, half generated by the base model and the other half from the SMART model, from the same set of 15 random prompts. The excerpts were presented in random order without labels. For the last three

participants, a page was added to the welcome screen stating the project funding the listening test. At the end of the study we obtain 407 ratings, as one participant failed to finish the test. From this, we remove 8 observations corresponding to 4 prompts that produced silent outputs from the base model. The total number of observations is thus 399. Figure 5 shows the distribution of ratings overall as well as per participant. To further consolidate the results, we fit a linear mixed effect model

$$y = X\beta + Zu + \varepsilon \tag{2}$$

where y are the ratings, $X\beta$ represents the fixed effects predictors and coefficients, Zu represent the random effects and ε are the residuals. The choice of model is dictated by the necessity to control for subject-dependent effects in the model. In our case the only fixed effect is applying SMART. The random effect include a random intercept and slope for the stimulus group and for the subject group. We implemented the model in R using the `lmer` package. Table 5 in the Appendix summarizes the results. We see that applying SMART has a significant ($p = 0.002$) positive effect on participants' ratings. On average, ratings increased by 1.22 points in the post condition compared to the baseline.

5 Discussion

5.1 How does SMART affect the model outputs?

The results indicate that SMART has a number effects on model behaviour. Post-SMART outputs have larger numbers of notes, increased rate of polyphony, zero empty beat rate, a wider pitch range, and a wider set of velocities. Additionally, the velocities of the post intervention model are lower. Listening to the outputs of the the two models reveals some differences, e.g., for music generated by the model adapted using SMART the number of pauses is reduced, and its dynamic range is increased. These factors could explain why the listeners find the SMART model's outputs more enjoyable on average. One interesting observation is that MAA ratings for some post-intervention model outputs (Figure 3) are higher than those of real performances (Table 1). This should not be interpreted as the model outputs being better than the real performances but rather shows the limitations of MAA as a proxy for human subjective experience.

5.2 What happens if we optimize more aggressively?

Figure 6: **Aggressive optimization of models towards the aesthetic reward results in high rewards but destroys diversity in outputs.** The distribution of Content Enjoyment scores (top) and average piano rolls from first 16 beats (bottom) computed on 1000 samples from the base model and three SMART models with progressively more aggressive optimization settings.

A known phenomenon in RL is that optimization towards a proxy reward past a critical point hurts performance on the true objective (Karwowski et al., 2024). To test how this manifests in our setting, we run SMART for 1000 iterations (instead of 200). To over-optimize further, we also set $\beta = 0.0$. Figure 6 shows the distributions of the resulting MAA ratings, and average piano rolls, generated by

the resulting models using 1000 random prompts. When optimizing more aggressively, we observe that the model’s outputs obtain higher ratings from MAA, but also that the average piano rolls show more distinct patterns, indicating reduced diversity in the outputs. The loss in diversity is consistent with earlier findings in the field of reinforcement from human feedback for LLMs (Kirk et al., 2024).

5.3 What if we use prompts from the pretraining set instead?

A consequence of the procedural prompts used during SMART is that we induce a domain shift relative to the pretraining data. Tempos and time signatures which are rare in the pretraining set are more represented in the procedural prompts. We wanted to understand if using prompts sampled from the pretraining dataset would result in a different overall outcome. Therefore, we apply SMART using the same settings as in Section 3.5 but now use prompts sampled from the training split of the pretraining dataset. We then sample 1000 prompts from the test split of the pretraining data and compute MAA scores and MIDI features on the outputs of the base model and the tuned model. Figure 7 shows increases in the MAA ratings and changes in MIDI features in this setting that are similar to as those observed in the procedural prompt setting.

Figure 7: MAA ratings and MIDI features for 1000 outputs from the base model and after 200 iterations of SMART. *Prompts extracted from the pretraining dataset.

6 Conclusions

This paper proposes SMART, a fine-tuning scheme that uses RL to optimize a symbolic music generation model using an aesthetic preference model in the audio domain as a reward. We study the effects of SMART on model outputs and find multiple notable differences between the outputs before and after this intervention, including more notes, less pauses, and more dynamics. A preliminary listening study shows that the SMART intervention results in an increase in enjoyability scores. However, testing the effect of the intervention on listeners from a wider demographic in a more formal study is necessary to see to what extent the same trend holds in the general population. Future work will test the proposed approach with different audio aesthetic preference models and extend the work to the multi-instrument setting.

7 Ethics Statement

Our pretraining dataset consists of a subset of the MetaMIDI dataset (Ens and Pasquier, 2021), which was collected by scraping publicly available websites. Our preliminary listening experiment involved no atypical conditions that required ethical review. For ethical aspects related to the development of MAA, we refer to Tjandra et al. (2025). Total carbon dioxide emissions associated with the compute in this project is 9.07 kg CO₂ eq as estimated by the ML CO₂ Impact calculator (Lacoste et al., 2019).

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9 Appendix

Table 3: Soundfonts used in experiments

Short Name	Full Name	URL
musescore	MuseScore General	musescore.org/en/handbook/3/soundfonts-and-sfz-files
fluidr3	FluidR3 GM	musescore.org/en/handbook/3/soundfonts-and-sfz-files
grandeur	The Grandeur D	musical-artifacts.com/artifacts/2992
sgm	SGM-V2.01-XG-2.04	archive.org/details/SGM-V2.01
yamaha	Yamaha-C5-Salamander-JNv5_1	sites.google.com/site/soundfonts4u/

Table 4: URLs for Piano Performances Referenced in Table 1

Performance	URL
Chopin - Waltz Op.69 No.2	www.youtube.com/watch?v=cxG-k0TMgaA
Ludovico Einaudi - Nuvole Bianche	www.youtube.com/watch?v=CQ8zg1IXZi8
Mozart - Piano Sonata No.16 K.545	www.youtube.com/watch?v=I_AX4R-d29o
Philip Glass - Etude No.6	www.youtube.com/watch?v=pjizB3A5g_0
Oscar Peterson - Someone to Watch Over Me	www.youtube.com/watch?v=hZwfCKixNj4
Brad Mehldau - My Favorite Things	www.youtube.com/watch?v=rmSoK4cfMfI
Keith Jarrett - Solar	www.youtube.com/watch?v=zCKobOe7Cww
Hiromi Uehara - Blackbird (Live)	www.youtube.com/watch?v=D0s0LkQpGyA
Lili Boulanger - Prelude in B Major	www.youtube.com/watch?v=vyi3dTxfFrM
John Cage - Sonata for Prepared Piano No.1	www.youtube.com/watch?v=niu7jy5mB5k
Nancarrow - Study for Player Piano No. 21	www.youtube.com/watch?v=hMnTWfZgunU

Table 5: Summary of Linear Mixed-Effects Model: $\text{rating} \sim \text{system} + (\text{system}|\text{id})$

Model Fit Statistics					
Number of observations					399
Groups (id)					14
Log-likelihood					-871.671
AIC					1755.343
Random Effects (by id)		Variance	Std. Dev.		
Intercept		0.830	0.911		
SMART		0.752	0.867		
Residual		4.194	2.048		
Correlation (Intercept, SMART)	0.488				
Fixed Effects	Estimate	2.5% CI	97.5% CI	SE	p-value
Intercept	4.075	3.520	4.631	0.284	< 0.001***
SMART	1.221	0.613	1.828	0.310	0.002**